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Future Stability Challenges: Stability Analysis in Microgrids

A mikrohálózatok várhatóan fontos szerepet fognak játszani az intelligens aktív elosztó hálózatokban és a megújuló energiaforrások elosztó rendszerbe történő integrálásában. Az energiahálózat működésének fontos szempontja a rendszer stabilitásának fenntartása. Számos hasonlóság mellett lényeges különbségek vannak a hagyományos közüzemi hálózatok és a mikrohálózatok stabilitása között, melyek többsége a méretbeli és a tehetetlenségbeli eltérésekből, valamint a megújuló energiaforrások integrálásából származnak. Ebben a cikkben bemutatjuk a mikrohálózatok stabilitásának alapvető fogalmait és a stabilitásuk elemzési módszereit, a hagyományos módszerekkel összehasonlítva.

Microgrids are expected to play a large role in smart active distribution grids and also in incorporating renewable energy resources into the distribution system. A very important question of power grid operation is the maintaining of system stability. There are many similarities but also significant differences between the stability of conventional utility grids and microgrids, most of which originate from the difference in size, inertia and penetration of renewable energy sources. In this paper we present the basic concepts of microgrid stability as well as a detailed classification of stability analysis methods in traditional grids and microgrids, according to small signal and large signal stability.

Keywords: **microgrid, stability, small signal stability, large signal stability.**

1. INTRODUCTION

Microgrids can be visualized as small blocks of today's energy grid which are able to disconnect and function separately from the utility grid. Microgrids provide a base for the incorporation of the intermittent renewable energy sources into the energy grid [1]. Aside from the environmental benefits, microgrids can also offer economic and operational benefits such as increased reliability and improved energy economics [2].

Identically with large utility grids, stability is an important question for microgrids, one which researchers both in academia and industry work on relentlessly [2]. However, the differences between microgrids and traditional power grids also change their behavior, which affects their stability. Thus, the stability of microgrids has to be treated differently, and the reexamination as well as adjustment of stability analysis methods is necessary.

In our work we give an overview of the stability analyses in microgrids – compared to the traditional grid – classified based on small signal and large signal stability. We discuss the advantages and disadvantages of the methods, as well as the differences between their applicability to traditional grids and microgrids. Additionally we will also present some international microgrid examples.

2. BASIC STABILITY CONCEPTS IN MICROGRIDS

In this section we present the main differences between utility grids and microgrids, which lead to the changes in the stability analysis of these systems.

The microgrid is an innovative technology which helps to integrate renewable energy sources into distribution systems [3]. It also provides additional benefits, like reduced peak loading, enhanced flexibility, emission reduction and reliability improvement of the local systems [4] [5].

Unlike the traditional utility grids, microgrids can operate – besides the grid connected mode – in an isolated, so-called islanded mode too. These two operation modes have a great impact on the system's stability. When the microgrid operates in grid connected mode, frequency is determined by the main grid. In this operation mode, the stability problems mainly involve the stability of individual components such as Distributed Energy Resources or local loads [6]. Contrary to that, in microgrids which are operating in isolated mode, the system frequency is no longer kept up by the main grid, so the various DERs (Distributed Energy Resources) must maintain it in a tolerable range. Additionally, in islanded microgrids the relatively low short circuit capacity poses a big concern, because small changes in the configuration can cause large deviations in voltage and frequency in such cases [7]. Hence it can be said that the microgrid operation in islanded mode is even more demanding than operation in traditional power systems.

The stability challenges of microgrids significantly differ from challenges in traditional power systems. One root of these dissimilarities is the considerable difference in size. Additionally, in microgrids the feeders are comparably short and often operated at medium voltage [8]. This results in a lower reactance to resistance ratio in microgrids. Hence, resulting from the dynamic performance and the mathematical relationships between voltages, active and reactive power flows are different than in large utility grids [9].

Microgrids also have a significantly lower inertia because the power is supplied by DERs and comparably small synchronous machines, what makes the question of stability even more complicated. Virtual Inertia is widely studied in order to mitigate these issues - in [9] we can see an example for this.

Besides the considerably lower inertia in microgrids, another important characteristic is the high uncertainty in the microgrid system, which arises because of the small

size of the grid, the lower number of loads and the intermittent and uncertain nature of the RES (Renewable Energy Sources) - such as wind turbines [10].

Possibly the most significant difference concerning stability analysis lies in the loading, since the loading in microgrids is typically unbalanced, while conventional stability analysis techniques and models assume a balanced system [7] [11].

Originating from the structural differences between microgrids and conventional power grids, there are unique stability characteristics which can be observed in microgrids. For example, in conventional power systems, voltage stability problems occur more frequently than frequency troubles, whereas in islanded microgrids, the maintaining of frequency is a major challenge due to the system inertia and RES. There are also certain phenomena in conventional grids, like inter-area oscillation and voltage collapse, which have not been observed in microgrids [7].

Figure 1. Illustration of the microgrid stability analysis classification

In microgrids, system variables are strongly coupled, resulting in the instability manifesting in all system variables. Because of this strong coupling, it is not practical to label the instability events as “voltage instability” or “frequency instability” based only on one system variable. Instead stability in a microgrid is usually categorized according to the cause of the instability, the size of the perturbation, the physical components that are involved in the process, the time-span of the instability event, and the methodology used for analyzing and predicting the instability [7]. In our work, we chose the classification according to the size of the perturbation into small signal and large signal stability. This provides an opportunity for a better comparison with the conventional stability analysis methods. In Figure 1, we can see an illustration of the

categorization of the most common stability analysis types according to small signal and large signal stability.

3. SMALL SIGNAL STABILITY

Small signal stability, also often referred to as steady state stability, deals with stability problems which occur after relatively small disturbances. These kinds of small disturbances are constantly present in electrical power grids, since they can be caused by load fluctuation, switching operations, etc. [12]. In a microgrid, the small signal disturbances are associated with feedback controllers, continuous load switching, the power limit of the micro sources, etc. [13].

Small signal stability in microgrids – just like in the large electric power systems – is mostly analyzed with the help of linearization (Eigenvalue and impedance analysis) but there are also some, for now less explored non-linear methods (e.g. bifurcation theory) [13].

Traditionally, small signal stability can be studied through eigenvalue analysis by developing state space models of the system [7]. It has also been observed that critical low-frequency modes are characterized by the tuning of inverters’ outer power sharing control loops, while critical high-frequency modes are influenced by the inverters’ inner voltage and current control loop [14].

Because microgrids are generally unbalanced networks, the development of state-space models is quite a complex task. This is why, for the steady state stability analysis of microgrids, a combination of dynamic simulations and signal processing methods has proven to be more effective (like for example the Prony method) [9].

Another important difference between the traditional power systems and microgrids is the large inertia and infinite bus of traditional systems, so small disturbances are less likely to substantially perturb the system whereas in microgrids these are more likely to cause significant problems in operation [7].

4. LARGE SIGNAL STABILITY

If we are dealing with system stability problems caused by large disturbances, we are talking about large signal stability issues, also called transient stability problems. Large disturbances in microgrids are mainly linked to short-circuits, unplanned transitions from grid-connected to islanded mode, and loss of generation units. Such disturbances can cause undamped oscillations, power swings, as well as large frequency and voltage excursions in the system [7].

A significant difference between the classical large power systems and microgrids is the possibility of islanding (isolation) in microgrids. If the disturbance causes an islanded mode of the microgrid, the critical clearing time (CCT) can help determine the relative stability. In the classical large power systems, equal area criterion analysis is usually used to determine the CCT. But this technique cannot be used in microgrids, since stability problems in microgrids are not directly linked to synchronism

problems among DERs. If the islanding in the microgrid was planned, it will result in less serious voltage and frequency excursions because the DERs set-points were already calculated and adjusted before the islanding [7].

The transient stability analysis in microgrids can usually be classified into the following three categories: Lyapunov based techniques, time-domain simulations, and hardware in the loop studies [9].

With the Lyapunov based techniques the proper representation of nonlinear system components and the large perturbations sustained by renewable energy sources is possible [9]. Maybe the most fundamental advantage of the Lyapunov based techniques is the possibility to estimate the region of attraction of stable operating points [2]. In the utility grid, the main problem of the Lyapunov based techniques lies in the complexity of the method. However, in microgrids there is a much smaller number of generators and buses which makes the system more manageable in regard of a Lyapunov based stability analysis [2].

Time-Domain simulation based stability analysis has several advantages, including high accuracy and validity (even more than Lyapunov based methods), as well as precise stability boundaries [7]. The disadvantages of the Time-Domain based methods lie in the computational intensity, and usually many such simulations are needed to ensure stability for a wide number of initial conditions and various disturbances [7]. For the time-domain simulations usually Electro-Magnetic Transient (EMT) tools are used, but in large microgrids these tools might prove to be unpractical because of the high computational complexity [9]. Transient Stability (TS) tools, also called electromechanical transient tools, may be an alternative solution for the computational complexity, but they were originally developed for balanced networks, so adjustments are needed to make them suitable for unbalanced microgrid networks (like for example adjustment with dynamic phasors [15]) [7].

Real-time HIL (Hardware in the Loop) simulations are considered to be an advanced and effective tool for stability analysis in microgrids [7]. HIL tools are especially effective in the analysis of DER components and their controls [7]. These tools can be categorized into two groups: Controller Hardware in the Loop (CHIL) and Power Hardware in the Loop (PHIL). With the Controller Hardware in the Loop methods, a hardware controller can be tested while it is connected to a Digital Real Time Simulator (DRTS) simulated microgrid network. The CHIL simulations can show the performance of control algorithms in realistic conditions such as time delays and noise [7]. In Power Hardware in the Loop methods the hardware under test (HuT) is connected to the real-life system simulated by the DRTS which allows testing under realistic conditions. Because the simulated system can be easily and quickly changed, the hardware's impact on the system under various circumstances can be tested conveniently.

5. MICROGRIDS AROUND THE GLOBE

There are various different microgrid projects all around the globe. We can find them in Europe, China, Japan, USA, Australia, Antarctica etc. Some have real life applications while others are used only for research. Some are established as a plant and some are virtually modelled [17].

Different regions can have different goals and focuses. For example, while in Japan the focus is on the reduction of the environmental impact of the electricity supply, in the USA the focus lies more on the reduction of investment in plant equipment and cost [18]. Microgrids in Asia however are mostly for remote application, where they focus on generating whatever amount of renewable energy is available for a reliable power system while maintaining stability.

To mention some of the bigger projects, we could name the following facilities [17]:

British Columbia Institute of Technology's microgrid testbed which is a scaled down microgrid used to be presented to utility companies and researchers.

Kyoto eco-energy microgrid testbed at Kythnos Island in Japan which is used to aid the existent grid.

The residential microgrid testbed at Albuquerque, New Mexico by Shimizu Institute of Technology which is a joint project of the USA and Japan.

Microgrid testbed in University of Seville, Spain, which is mainly solar energy based and uses an electrolyzer placed in the main power distribution line to overcome the unpredictable nature of the energy source. When more power is generated than needed, it is stored in the form of hydrogen which can be used when necessary [17].

We can see that microgrids around the world are often utilized, but also researched – this is no wonder, since they could very well be the cornerstone of the power distribution grid of the future.

6. SUMMARY

To summarize, there are considerable differences between the traditional and microgrid stability challenges. These mainly arise from the differences in size, inertia, loading and operating modus (grid connected/islanded).

Because of the strong connection between the microgrid variables, a classification into small and large signal stability is preferable for microgrids.

Small signal stability in microgrids as well as in the traditional grids is usually analyzed with the help of linearization. We have to note that small signal stability is more emphasized in microgrids because in these kinds of systems small perturbations are more likely to cause significant problems. Meanwhile, large signal stability analysis in microgrids can be categorized into three groups: Lyapunov based techniques, time-domain simulation-based stability analysis and real-time HIL simulations.

Some traditionally used methods are not suitable to be utilized in microgrids (like equal area criterion)

whereas other methods maybe more effective in microgrids than in traditional grids (like Lyapunov based techniques). This is why microgrid stability is fertile ground for further research.

7. REFERENCES

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